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THE CHALLENGES AND TRENDS OF HOTEL ADMINISTRATION THAT TRANSITION AFTER PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT

The scope of this article is the challenges and trends in hotel management that are emerging after the COVID-19 pandemic, bringing aspects that impacted hotel management after the pandemic, which demonstrated certain difficulties that had consequences for the performance of this sector throughout Brazil, noting that, there were various phases that affected the economy and tourism with significant consequences that there was a need to interrupt operations, therefore, after facing the crisis, major challenges emerged that established the increase in strategies to focus on the sustainable growth of this sector. The general objective of this work is to analyze the challenges and trends of hotel management that emerge after the pandemic. As for the methodology used in this article, it uses a qualitative approach, bibliographical and documentary research, which were taken from the Google Scholar platform and reliable internet sites, which provided books, articles, magazines and materials that were important for the discussion of this article. In this way, responding to the problem in question, it was possible to see that the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on hotel management incorporated greater performance strategies based on changes and adjustments to activities. In general, the challenges and trends underwent a new perspective, concluding that the new mechanisms adopted intensified this network, establishing a commitment to sustainability, quality in services and experiences that offer guests well-being in accordance with the individuality of guests. same.

Keywords: Pandemic, Hotel Administration, COVID-19.

INTRODUÇÃO

The hotel sector is quite complex, due to its constant changes that align with current affairs. As a result, in 2019, the COVID-19 pandemic emerged, bringing impacts to the Brazilian hotel industry, which resulted in several phases. The consequences were negatively exposed, resulting in the suspension of travel, demands for stoppages that administratively affected the hotel chain around the world. However, after the pandemic period, this sector began to reopen with a varied drop in occupancy, that is, a low level of accommodation due to the virus variants.

Given this context, this work is justified, bringing aspects that impacted hotel administration after the pandemic, which demonstrated certain difficulties that constituted impacts on the performance of this sector throughout Brazil, noting that there were varied phases that affected the economy and the tourism with significant consequences that there was a need to interrupt operations, therefore, after facing the crisis, major challenges emerged that established the increase in strategies to focus on the sustainable growth of this sector.

Analyzing this subject, the issue in question is what are the challenges and trends of hotel management that are emerging after the pandemic? In hypothesis, this sector in the post-COVID-19 pandemic, resisted the main health complexity in the country, where administratively, it had medium and long-term preparation to face everything from restrictions to the growth of this branch, which has been accelerating worldwide, with technological enhancements, personalization and experiences.

The general objective of this work is to analyze the challenges and trends of hotel management that emerge after the pandemic. While the specific objectives are: understanding aspects of hotel administration; identify the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on hotel management; and discuss the challenges and trends in the hotel administrative segment that are emerging after the pandemic.

As for the methodology used in this article, it uses a qualitative approach, bibliographical and documentary research, which were taken from the Google Scholar platform and reliable internet sites, which provided books, articles, magazines and materials that were important for the discussion of this article.

The first section was about aspects of hotel management, discussing the emergence of this sector, in addition to its broad segment in the industrial market, which has been growing rapidly in Brazil with national and international trends that are influenced by tourism and the economy, driving the challenges administrative, as it requires efforts that must meet the needs of customers.

The second section is about the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on hotel management, bringing authors who discuss the consequences that affected this chain in an alarming way, which were enough to close several projects in Brazil and around the world. Therefore, its massive effects generated complexities in resuming activities in this segment.

The third section presents the challenges and trends in the hotel administrative segment that are emerging after the pandemic, showing, after the pandemic, the positive impacts of an economic crisis that it managed to overcome with its strategies. Where it presents that there is importance when developing strategic planning and with this, the administrative organization seeks to outline its goals, identifying and solving the complexities that need to be faced.

The relevance of this work is established by the way in which hotel administrators boosted the hotel sector after the COVID-19 pandemic, considering that this subject is important for the academic community and researchers, who can further their research or expand this topic for debate, which, in turn, is quite scarce.

ASPECTS OF HOTEL ADMINISTRATION

Brazil, in terms of hospitality, emerged in the same way as Europe, which began with the

Portuguese, where on Brazilian soil people began to receive travelers in their own homes. In the colonial period, these individuals were hosted in monasteries and colleges. Currently, accommodation enterprises and hotels are important bases in the tourism chain that, in turn, interact in economic sectors (Souza, 2019).

In the Brazilian region, in Tupiniquin lands, the hotel sector began using schools, houses and monasteries to welcome travelers. During this period, the bandeirantes always traveled to look for silver or gold and take it to the Portuguese Crown, always changing frequently in the intention of the local precious stones. In the middle of the 19th century, the big boost came with the movement of people to use the São Paulo Railway Line trains, as well as trade between Rio de Janeiro and São Paulo, which also contributed to the expansion.

For Pereira (2015, p. 510), the hotel sector over the years has become “accessible to different social layers, due to the improvement in means of communication and transport that contributed to the reduction of distances and costs, facilitating the movement of people”.

Currently, the hotel sector is expanding, serving people seeking leisure, business or family trips. Therefore, this trend must also be attractive with its demand for hotels throughout Brazil, offering possibilities for home office work, which remodel the delivery of short or extended stay services, as well as the care required for their health. In this sense, the country’s hotel industry needs to make new uses of its spaces, creating

intelligent ways that adapt to the current needs of the tourism sector.

As perspectivas de crescimento da indústria hoteleira no Brasil são promissoras, em função da relativa estabilização da economia do país e do aumento acentuado das viagens turísticas nos dois últimos anos, o que significa que a estabilização da moeda e dos preços conduziu à incorporação do item viagens ao orçamento familiar, pelo menos entre a classe média. As viagens turísticas ao exterior apresentam um componente importante para a hotelaria brasileira: os turistas brasileiros, 80 por cento dos quais se destinam aos Estados Unidos, passam a conhecer o padrão da hotelaria de países desenvolvidos, que apresentam melhor qualidade e menores preços. Gradualmente, esses turistas irão pressionar as empresas do setor hoteleiro no Brasil a oferecer mais qualidade e preços menores (Governo do Estado do Ceará, 2011, p. 26).

Taking all this into account, it is noted that the hotel sector has its aspects within the needs that drive the tourism sector, such as, for example, the so-called “extended stays”, which means prolonged stays, which have once and for all gained the preference of many tourists. , making all services consistent with guest safety enjoyable. Such trends are increasingly gaining ground, opening a broad perspective that joins various services that are aligned with tourism, in order to satisfy economic growth.

According to data from IBGE (Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics):

Graph 1: Number of accommodation establishments by type, 2016

Source: IBGE (2024).

Correlating to IBGE data, in 2022, the tourism sector was one of the “main responsible for the 2.9% growth in Brazil’s Gross Domestic Product (GDP), totaling R\$ 727 billion, in addition to accounting for more than 7, 6 million jobs” (Ministry of tourism, 2023 a, b apud Souza, 2019, p. 09).

It is important to highlight that the modern hotel sector has become a habit of identifying the segment as a hotel industry, however, it cannot be said that it is industrialized, as it does not manufacture anything. Analyzing by way of illustration, this sector provides food, accommodation, entertainment and service provision. It defines a hotel as a building that has a location, preferably urban, where it normally has several floors, offering accommodation and a structure aimed at business and leisure.

When talking about the hotel industry in Brazil within the growth perspectives, it is noted that they are promising, due to the relative stabilization of the economy in Brazil, as well as the marked increase in tourist travel in recent years, mainly abroad, implying that all this means that the stability of prices and currency led to the incorporation of the item into the family budget, which includes the middle class in this condition. It is important to highlight an important component for this sector that includes Brazilian tourists, 80 percent are destined for international countries, with the aim of presenting a hotel standard from developed countries, with better quality and lower prices assigned (Government of the State of Ceará, 2011).

Analyzing this context, it is noted that international hotel chains entered Brazil, with the growth in the economy, implementing multinational business branches that are a result of current changes in the country, constituting an intensification of its competition and transforming it into an important hub for travel and business. Its facilities integrated large sectors, coinciding with the economic forms and incentives for the construction of hotels, establishing it as an enterprise that became relevant due to its function in each social structure.

A Hotelaria sempre esteve presente no percurso

da história humana e participou ativamente no desenvolvimento econômico brasileiro e mundial, da Era Antiga aos dias atuais; estando sempre atrelada a atividade turística e a evolução tecnológica que proporcionou: melhores condições de transporte aéreo com ascensão da indústria aeronáutica dos aviões a jato e grandes aviões, a sofisticação dos navios de cruzeiros, os ônibus especiais para transporte de passageiros e principalmente a evolução da comunicação (Governo do Estado do Ceará, 2011, p. 20).

Therefore, the hotel sector is a broad enterprise, which constitutes its varied structures that go beyond tourist demand in the search for leisure or work, therefore, this branch has an extensive expansion due to its growth that establishes factors linked to tourism, which It is always constantly renewing within a competitive market, bringing challenges that are faced by national or international entrepreneurs, such as competition that presents habits that tend to change.

THE IMPACTS OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON HOTEL ADMINISTRATION

As seen, hotel management was one of the sectors that weakened during the COVID-19 pandemic, as it was unable to boost the tourism segment in Brazil. In 2020, the increase in coronavirus cases increased significantly, affecting accommodations, which, in turn, had a negative impact on this sector, which led to the isolation and closure of several chains, resulting in an accelerated reduction in employees and guests. All of this was the result of the drop in tourism, which is also correlated with the country’s economy, presenting extreme situational difficulties.

Furthermore, it can be said that the COVID-19 pandemic is a disease that has a health severity and its contamination is accelerated as it affects several countries around the world, making it difficult to maintain control. It should be noted that situational changes in the world presented various extreme complexities, mainly in the fluctuations of economic demands, geological risks, social problems, political instability, among other aspects that caused pandemic risks (Cypriano, 2014). Soon, public health in Brazil

experienced a major outbreak, compromising hotel management throughout the country.

Restrictions during the COVID-19 pandemic have affected the hospitality sector, leaving several hotels empty and several employees unemployed. This whole situation has made tourism eminent, negatively affecting travel, due to the quarantine that led to a sharp decrease in occupations. The impacts had a greater meaning, in terms of accommodation cancellations, as well as the organization of support for travelers. This pandemic scenario presented challenging ways in which administrators had to act quickly when making administrative and managerial decisions.

O Turismo e a Hotelaria são setores que estão intimamente vinculados por se assentarem na dimensão humana. A hotelaria foi um dos grandes setores turísticos mais afetados. Pois é uma parte do sistema do turismo e, como tal, interage com as demais partes. Isso significa que existe uma interdependência entre o hotel e os demais integrantes do sistema: o hotel influencia o resultado do conjunto, assim como sofre influências das outras partes. E diante do cenário de pandemia, surge um consumidor mais desconfiado e exigente. Pois neste momento pesa a questão da biossegurança no setor do Turismo em geral (Silva, 2020, p. 124).

Above all, many hotel managers had to guarantee the survival of the hotel sector, bringing innovations and competitive advantages for the purpose of recovery after the pandemic. Due to the complexities of the coronavirus, many entrepreneurs had to create different strategies, so that they brought organizational motivations that influenced competitiveness, among other measures adopted that constituted administrative control, and increased the hotel segment. It is important to highlight that services were reduced, however, this branch had to follow Legislative Decree No. 6 of March 20, 2020 established by the World Health Organization (WHO).

According to Silva (2020, p. 126), he explains that “the travel and hotel sectors were the most impacted by the pandemic, according to the main entities and experts representing these sectors”.

However, the shutdown of the hotel sectors during the COVID-19 pandemic changed the entire structure of its effects, which administrators

needed to reinvent to maintain the sustainability of activities and their planning. Furthermore, most hotel entrepreneurs had to create ideas observed around the world, mainly in terms of safety protocols, in order to strengthen until the arrival of the vaccine. Analyzing the impacts, the difficulties in this network were one of the main nightmares and challenges in establishing the recovery.

Segundo dados recentes da Confederação Nacional do Comércio de Bens, Serviços e Turismo (CNC), o setor da hotelaria em 2020 teve um prejuízo de R\$ 62 bilhões, acrescenta-se que a retomada pós pandemia poderá ser mais lenta e causar 300 mil desempregos no setor. Salienta-se que o turismo responde por 3,71% do PIB do País e a perspectiva é de que a atividade econômica do setor pode ter caído 39% em 2020 (Mecca; Gedoz, 2020 apud Lopes; Freitas; Vargas, 2022, p. 03).

With the aim of reducing the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic, the hotel chain had to establish a gradual return to activities, consolidating with tourism and other segments that encompass culture, with the aim of implementing accommodation facilities during isolation taking into account consideration of forms of seasons that correlate with the pandemic situation, which were established with priority assistance for risk groups, rigorous hygiene, training for employees, strengthening the use of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE), among other aspects (Tomé, 2020).

Above all, hotel administration in many states in Brazil had its activities suspended, due to the significant drop in accommodation in most hotels. Furthermore, this sector had to reopen and help employees adapt to the social distancing protocol, following all necessary recommendations. It should be noted that the majority of projects suffered severe impacts, with many declaring bankruptcy, while others sought financing as a way of trying to lift the sector in the hotel market.

Em estudo realizado pelo Fórum de Operadores Hoteleiros do Brasil (FOHB), em maio a taxa de propriedades fechadas era de 65%. Para o mês de junho, o indicador teve queda para 52%, e a tendência é cair ainda mais em julho. A entidade aponta na previsão de abertura

que três em cada quatro hotéis têm previsão de reabertura para o mês de junho e julho. Em um novo levantamento realizado pelo Fórum, 24,6% dos entrevistados pretendem retomar as operações em junho, enquanto 49% devem reabrir em julho. Hoje, o Brasil conta com 48% de sua oferta hoteleira em funcionamento. Na pesquisa, foram entrevistadas 65 redes hoteleiras, 884 hotéis, somando 142.892 Unidades habitacionais (UH's) em 26 estados e 209 municípios no período de 15/06 a 21/06/2020 (Silva, 2020, p. 126).

Observing the impacts of hotel management during the pandemic, financial issues are a recurring problem in several countries, bringing catastrophic consequences that made reopening impossible. Other complexities faced in this sector were the adaptation of protocols, management problems, reduction of employees and the insertion of technological instruments. The strategies used were the termination of activities and the closure of the enterprise, aiming to analyze spending control, planning and assertive decision-making.

According to Silva (2020, p. 135), the “hotel sector in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. We sought to understand the new times for the Brazilian hotel industry, the impacts of the pandemic on issues of tourist mobility”, changing habits and patterns in the hosting culture for companies in this service network.

Therefore, the new standards of hotel administration services brought new actions that made it possible to attract customers during this period, in addition to expressing that technological tools were one of the positive strategies, as they became essential to understanding the means that seek to implement the corrective changes that were became uncertain during this period and corroborated inherent challenges that made it possible to correct the possible weaknesses that were found during that time, that is, there was an increase that accelerated the hotels.

THE CHALLENGES AND TRENDS OF THE HOTEL ADMINISTRATIVE SEGMENT THAT TRANSITION AFTER PANDEMIC

As seen, the world entered into public calamity with the arrival of the COVID-19 pandemic, where human beings, due to lack of knowledge about the virus, needed to use various prevention methods due to the contamination rate, such as, for example, use of masks. Above all, the varied impacts also resulted in the overload of health professionals, who began to experience atypical situations, such as hospitalizations, excessive use of materials, leading them to work double shifts, which means that these complexities faced, It also impacted the hotel administrative segment which, in turn, underwent gradual changes after the pandemic period.

The COVID-19 pandemic shook the world economy, especially in Brazil, where commercial establishments and entertainment activities began to close, ending their work due to economic losses that, in fact, resulted in a high unemployment rate. Therefore, in the hotel sector, the crisis had an impact on several factors, knowing that all the challenges faced by hotel entrepreneurs had logistical and human difficulties, which demonstrated that the complexities in administration during this period have possible solutions (Silva; Oliveira, 2021).

After the COVID-19 pandemic, it began with several uncertainties and challenges for hotel administration, modifying, among many factors, work routines and human relations, among other aspects. Such changes had to structure the logic for the free movement of people, considering the implementation of guest service protocols, disinfection and sanitation of places, cleaning, etc. All of these are impacts that have established new trends and challenges for sustainable practices in the vast majority of hotel chains, as it is an environmental issue relevant to the growth of this sector.

Na cadeia turística, a indústria da hotelaria é o segmento que mais empregos oferecem e tem maior efeito no desenvolvimento das regiões onde atua (Segarra-Oña et al, 2012). Pode-se

então dizer que há uma relação inevitável entre o desenvolvimento da indústria hoteleira, os impactos ambientais e a necessidade de maior eficiência no consumo de recursos (Cingoski; Petrevska, 2018 apud Lopes; Freitas; Vargas, 2022, p. 03).

Another trend in hotel management after the pandemic was technological innovations, which had an intense impact on the issue of adaptation and learning, since its adoption was important to increase and strengthen this sector, by bringing guarantees and competitiveness. In this trade, therefore, the transformations were a response to the changes in this environment, the use of tools changed the entire process to the current scenario, in an accelerated and enhanced way, resulting in faster ways to face new challenges.

According to Gaspar (2022, p. 10), after the COVID-19 pandemic, “inevitably associated with the radical change in the tourism model and the beginning of a major transformation in the hotel industry. Although some sectors have suffered minor consequences”, however, this sector has managed to increase its segments almost completely, occupying levels that have strengthened the environmental conditions and emerging opportunities in this industry.

It should be noted that the protocols implemented after the COVID-19 pandemic were intended to provide everyone involved in the hotel sector with safety conditions in terms of sanitary measures, where sustainability policies in control and prevention had to be established. From the point of view of administrators or managers in the hotel sector. It is known that tourism also suffered negative impacts, however, the transformations arising from changes in environmental, cultural, social, economic sustainability and institutional policies were enough to return to normality.

Based on studies by Lopes; Freitas; Vargas (2022), Brazil has had several changes regarding the sustainability of the hotel sector in the post-pandemic context, as the greatest demand from guests was hotels with natural resources (trails, outdoor tours, outdoor sports), in addition to local culture), as well as consumption in local businesses, which increased the economic and social dimensions. Above all, administrative

experiences aligned with private tourism benefit the hotel sector, due to the high level of trips destined for ecotourism. In view of the above, the demand from users focused on well-being tends to provide greater growth in the hotel chain.

It can be seen that the challenges and needs resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic were fundamental for the administration to be efficient and capable in its strategies, which overcame difficulties and improved working conditions for both employees and guests. Furthermore, being responsible for managing, organizing, controlling and coordinating all tasks within an environment, reconciling financial, human and physical resources, is the responsibility of the manager responsible for this condition and work issues.

For Silva; Oliveira (2021, p. 24):

Implementar um processo de planejamento em uma organização significa promover a mudança, pois se tal processo responde a vários problemas abrangentes, podemos ver uma série de ações que vão desencadear a relação entre pessoas, tecnologia e sistemas. As mudanças devem ser planejadas para alcançar o sucesso esperado. O planejamento é uma das alternativas que as organizações usam para promover mudanças estruturais, tecnológicas, de infraestrutura e quaisquer outras que sejam necessárias. Implementar o planejamento estratégico em uma organização é um meio apropriado para promover mudanças estruturais de longo prazo.

The hotel sector, after the COVID-19 pandemic, integrated the tourism infrastructure, representing a significant portion, as it is associated through its services, incorporating various innovations that circumvented the crisis, such as, for example, artificial intelligence, the use of cloud computing, systems integration, internet of things, cyber security, robotics, among other aspects. Due to the acceleration of technological changes, the preferences and consumption needs of human beings in terms of accommodation have also changed, becoming a challenge and trend for hotel chain administrators.

According to Gaspar (2022, p. 10), he highlights that, “although the adoption of these digital tools

and innovations can represent a competitive advantage, the topic is not always disseminated to managers about which tools to adopt”, that is, how which services are concentrate and how to use.

It is impossible to measure that the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic affected different contexts, in an unexpected situation, which after this period, the hotel administration had to establish strategies that resulted in positive results, therefore, the greater flow of people was part of this sector in accelerated growth, which allowed us to understand administrative determinations in a coherent way for a new reconfiguration of standards, presenting good performances, a marketing plan to attract new customers, home office for a positive trend, among other results.

Exemplifying these issues, below is a comparison of before and after the COVID-19 pandemic, of Hotel Chain occupancy until July 2022:

Table 1: Occupancy of the Hotel Network until July 2022

Julho	
Ano	Ocupação
2017	48,95%
2020	13,80%
2021	12,32%
2022	60,04%

Source: Bittar (2023, p. 15).

Analyzing this data, it is clear that after the pandemic, there was a long period of investigation, where various commercial sectors as a whole and administrators individually, had to change the ways in which they performed their functions. It can be said that it was through technology that the hotel network was improved so that customers could make their stays, in other words, new trends and challenges came along with the changes in these networks. Relatively, along with tourism, they had to innovate ways to guarantee survival in the market, therefore, occupations started to increase significantly, responding to good management that made a crisis, segments that lifted this hotel industry.

According to Timothy; Delgado (2023, p. 4), explains that “the hotel chain and more

specifically the Events sector, had to modify its management and operational processes”, highlighting that the administration of this sector was crucial to support all challenges to the new situation, following all activities in a positive or negative way, which, in turn, outlined strategies to deal with all the adversities that arose during the pandemic.

It is possible to understand that the hotel chain is any and all types of commerce, where people stay for purposes that go beyond leisure to work, and which are speculated and planned according to each individuality, which are scheduled in advance, with similar objectives or according to collective needs.

It is possible to understand that:

[...] o turismo e a hotelaria trabalham de tal maneira que a hospedagem assume o papel de se tornar objeto de consumo turístico, onde o próprio empreendimento disponibiliza uma estrutura de hospedagem e entretenimento, contribuindo com a economia local na qual está inserido, pois suas atividades ajudam a movimentar o circuito econômico. É possível observar tal fenômeno em muitas cidades que têm suas economias dependentes do setor turístico, hoteleiro e de Eventos.

Given this understanding, the seriousness of the situation caused by the Covid-19 pandemic involved a lot of planning, where many hotel administrators found themselves forced to plan activities to adapt their resources in light of the new complex demands, which resulted in this sector. in a positive way, due to the strong efforts in the situations. Therefore, the adoptions taken by the hotel administration propagated actions that triggered the growth of this sector, minimizing impacts within a sphere of challenges and positive trends.

CONCLUSION

Analyzing the entire context of this article, we can see an approach that helps to evaluate the hotel sector and its management in restoring its growth after the COVID-19 pandemic. Noting that control for its recovery required medium to long-term strategic plans, also noting that the experiences of the virus in relation to its

contamination affected this branch, which, in turn, needed customized solutions to meet and align with the tourist and economic trends.

Realizing the first objective, regarding the aspects of hotel administration, he noted that its history was broad, marked by global expansion, which established positive consequences, due to its accelerated growth and linked to tourism. Notably, its power in Brazil began to be perceived and strengthened the country's economy on several levels, envisioning the optimistic future that emerged at a prominent point, by presenting a hotel administrator that leads positively in its sustainability.

Observing the second objective on the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on hotel administration, it was identified that the main complexities caused during the pandemic period slowed down the economy, and that the various enterprises had to adopt strategies to improve such issues involving this network, within a new reality that allows growth and new adaptations. It was also noticed that the adoption of measures established a strategic planning that was assertive for the changes.

The third objective regarding the challenges and trends of the hotel administrative segment that transition after the pandemic, showed that the difficulties were gradually overcome, where the manager knew how to deal with the complexities, establishing strategies that became viable for improving the hotel crisis. Notably, the insertion of technological tools promoted for this sector had a positive impact on the entire context involving this network, which currently has great growth in this industry.

In this way, responding to the problem in question, it was possible to see that the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on hotel management incorporated greater performance strategies based on changes and adjustments to activities. In general, the challenges and trends underwent a new perspective, concluding that the new mechanisms adopted intensified this network, establishing a commitment to sustainability, quality in services and experiences that offer guests

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